

Newsletter EURCAW-Poultry-SFA

15 December 2025, Edition 14

Questions to EURCAW-Poultry-SFA (Q2E)

All Q2E answers are available [online](#).

 Q2E-Poultry-SFA-2025-005: Pre-stun shocks in waterbath stunning of Poultry (ongoing)

 Q2E-Poultry-SFA-2025-007: [Broiler Cannibalism Emergency Measures](#)

 Q2E-Poultry-SFA-2025-008: duck catching (ongoing)

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→ The Q2E webform is available online [here](#) or <https://survey.anses.fr/SurveyServer/s/DSL/QuerywebformIQ3/questionnaire.htm>

→ You can download [here](#) the webform in PDF to prepare your Q2E submission.

★ Knowledge Pill: How long can they stand?

The Centre is proud to present its first **Knowledge Pill: How long can they stand?** *Determining the walking ability in broilers using the latency-to-lie test.*

Walking ability is a relevant animal-based indicator of welfare in broilers. The most commonly used method to assess the walking ability of broilers is the gait scoring, but its subjectivity can make comparison between farms scored by different observers difficult.

This has led to the development of the more objective latency-to-lie test that is highly linked with gait scores. This Knowledge Pill provides a short explanation about the two scoring systems and a visual explanation about how to perform them.

Click [here](#) to watch!

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2025 Highlights

Four EURCAWs meeting with EU Animal Welfare NRCs and SBs

On **15 December 2025**, the **four EURCAWs** organized an online workshop entitled **EURCAW novel ‘welfare inspection support tool’** for the EU Animal Welfare Member State official inspectors/officials. A total of **13 participants** attended the workshop. Excluding EURCAW members, **8 participants from 8 EU Member States** were present.

The workshop used a co-design process to ensure that the tool addressed the established needs of official inspectors, as an end-user. Three key elements were explored through the co-design process:

- The primary purposes for using the inspection tool.
- The types of content official inspectors expect to access through the tool.
- The technical and technological features that should be incorporated into the tool.

★ Selection of the most appropriate depopulation method for the welfare of poultry

In collaboration with EURCAW-Poultry-SFA, **FRCAW** developed a **guide for selecting the most appropriate depopulation method from an animal welfare perspective**, taking into account the different depopulation contexts encountered in cases of avian influenza (i.e., depending on the species affected, the farming system involved, and the resources available). This guide, published in early 2025 in the form of a nested hierarchy of decision trees, aims to provide operational support to the competent authorities of European Union Member States in choosing the methods to be implemented.

Selection of the most appropriate depopulation method for the welfare of poultry

In order to facilitate access and support its use in an operational context, this guide is **now available in interactive digital format**. This online version allows for more user-friendly consultation and facilitates the use of the tool in emergency situations.

This selection guide has been developed for competent authorities, but it is available to any interested party. It is structured as a hierarchy of decision trees designed to determine whether a given depopulation method can be used while ensuring poultry welfare.

Access to the online selection guide [here](#).

★ Season's Greetings!

The EURCAW-Poultry-SFA team wishes you a joyful holiday season and a prosperous New Year ahead! See you in 2026 with new animal welfare content!

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